

Emerging technologies: an AMD MI250X GPU-based platform for HPC applications

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1 Introduction

The last few years has seen an increased prevalence of GPU-based systems in national high-performance computing (HPC) services in many countries. A striking example is the United States Exascale programme, where almost all present and foreseeable top-tier supercomputing services have a GPU component. (For a recent review of the Exascale scene, see e.g., [1].) While the current UK ARCHER2 national service has no GPU component, a number of second tier research council services do, including the Cirrus [2] and Tursa services [3]. These services typically — although not exclusively — use NVIDIA technology. It is therefore of particular interest that in 2022, the ARCHER2 support team was given access by HPE to an AMD-based technology to allow the investigation described in this short report.

The purpose of this investigation was not to perform a detailed analysis or comparison of application performance, or concentrate on other technical measures. Rather, it was to gain familiarity with a new technology, and to try to make a judgement about how easily developers and support staff might undertake the typical activities — compilation, debugging, and so on — that are required when moving to a new platform. This involves the system software, compilers, tools and the user software environment. A number of specific questions were formulated:

1. How easy would it be to compile and run a range of user applications?
2. How would the level of debugging and profiling support compare against that available on the existing ARCHER2 service?
3. Could initial performance measures for applications be squared with expectations?
4. Could existing training material be adapted to the new platform?

These questions feed in to the broader question: could the ARCHER2 team provide a necessary and sufficient level of support to users and developers if such a platform became available as part of a future UK service?

The report describes the details of the MI250X systems available and other relevant background information in Section 2, and goes on to the findings of the study in Section 3.

The conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2 Background

Two HPE test-bed machines with identical GPU hardware were available to the study: `marvin4` and `pinoak`. Both were based on AMD MI250X technology. This is the same architecture as the Crusher service at Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility [4]. In this section, an overview of the architecture is provided (exact details are relegated to Appendix A). A brief overview of GPU programming models is also provided, limited to models relevant for the discussion of compilers and applications used here.

2.1 Hardware description

The host architecture involved nodes with one AMD EPYC 7A53 64 64-core processor with four 16-core NUMA regions and a total of 512 GB of DRAM. Each node hosted 4 AMD MI250X GPUs (being 8 logical GPU devices). The `marvin4` machine had 32 nodes, while `pinoak` had 30 nodes.

The AMD Instinct MI200 Series of accelerators includes the following AMD product releases: MI210, MI250 and MI250X. Each variant follows the CDNA2 architecture [5]. In this architecture, a GPU device contains two Graphics Complex Dies (GCDs), or chiplets. Each GCD has four *neighborhoods* also known as compute engines. Each compute engine has two columns of 14 compute units, where each compute unit has 64 cores (stream processors). Therefore, the entire GPU has 224 compute units. The number of compute units enabled depends on the variant: 104 for the MI210, 216 for the MI250 and 220 for the MI250X. All the compute engines within a GCD share the same 8MB L2 cache, and each GCD has 64GB of high bandwidth memory (HBM_e). Although there are four MI250X devices per node, the user sees eight separate logical GPU devices, each one corresponding to a specific MI250X GCD.

Host device data transfer was via AMD Infinity Fabric (two links per NUMA region giving one link per GPU device). Direct GPU to GPU data transfer is also via Infinity Fabric. The number of links ranges from four (intra-GCD) to one or two (between pairs of

GCDs). There are four network interface cards per node. The four are directly connected to the four MI250X via PCIe Gen4. This opens the way to direct data transfer between GPUs on different nodes without the overhead of intermediate host-device transfers.

2.2 GPU programming models

A number of models are used in GPU programming, and are supported by AMD [10]. A very brief overview of the models relevant to this study is given here. It is also convenient to discuss communication methods specifically relating to GPU models here. Some familiarity with GPU programming concepts is assumed.

2.2.1 Directives: OpenMP and OpenACC

Compiler directives provide a relatively quick and easy way to introduce thread-level (or loop-level) parallelism into C/C++, and Fortran codes. In the GPU context, directives are particularly relevant to Fortran, as other models are generally based on C or C++. The catch is that the compiler must provide support for the relevant hardware and, historically, this has been somewhat slow to emerge. A schism among the faithful has also given rise to two different standards of directive: OpenMP and OpenACC. These have broadly the same features, although compiler support varies.

2.2.2 HIP

The Heterogeneous Interface for Portability (HIP) is AMD's analogue of NVIDIA's programming model CUDA. In fact, it is a shim layer which allows C/C++ programmers to write code in the style of CUDA, and follows exactly the same programming model and programming interface. For example, calls to `cudaMalloc()` are replaced by calls to `hipMalloc()`, and so on. Most common CUDA run-time API routines have analogues, although not all recent CUDA functionality is available (e.g., the CUDA graph API). HIP might be considered the main AMD GPU programming model at the time of writing.

HIP supports the unified memory model of CUDA, where data in host memory and device memory (having different address spaces) may be transferred automatically as required

by the run-time. This is less effort for the programmer than explicit transfers, particularly for codes with complex data transfer patterns.

2.2.3 Kokkos

Kokkos is a C++ abstraction layer for portability between architectures developed by Sandia [6]. It provides a uniform programming interface to back ends which include HIP. Kokkos is used in a number of significant scientific applications such as LAMMPS (see below).

2.2.4 OpenCL and SYCL

Open computing language (OpenCL) is a relatively low level C programming model aiming to deal generally with "accelerators", of which GPUs are an example. While having considerable importance in the mobile and games market, it has had little significant penetration into the area of scientific applications owing at least in part to the rather awkward kernel model (kernels originally had to be expressed as strings in the code). The games market is now putting considerable effort into a more modern C++ approach SYCL [7], which is an abstraction layer requiring a level of compiler support.

OpenCL is mentioned here because it is used in GROMACS (see below). However, at the time of writing GROMACS is moving away from OpenCL and towards SYCL [8].

2.3 Applications

In selecting a number applications to try on the AMD system, the report has attempted to cover a range of scientific application areas, and a range of programming languages and GPU models. Further details appear in the following Section. A notable exception in the ARCHER2 context was VASP: this was not considered at the time owing to uncertainty about the level of support for the GPU programming model used (OpenACC). In addition, VASP is not a publicly available source. It is not the intention of the report to discuss machine learning applications.

3 Findings

The interactive environment on the front-end nodes of these new systems would be very familiar to users of ARCHER2. The marvin4 system used Cray Programming Environment CPE 22.06 while pinoak, used slightly later in the year, had CPE 22.10. The usual module system allowed selection of appropriate compilers and so on. The scheduling system was SLURM.

The AMD software stack Radeon Open Compute Platform, or ROCm, provides compilers and tools specific for their GPU systems. For example, the underlying HIP compiler is `hipcc`. The ROCm compiler machinery was integrated into the programming environments such as `PrgEnv-cray` and `PrgEnv-gnu`. To compile HIP code, either `hipcc`, or the relevant compiler wrapper can then be used. For directives-based methods, the compiler wrappers (`cc`, `CC` or `ftn`) were again used with appropriate options.

Basic compilation and execution tests were performed with a range of tutorial style examples, including those from the existing Cirrus GPU Programming course: OpenACC in C and Fortran, OpenCL in C [9], and Kokkos tutorials available with the installation (using both the OpenMP and HIP backends). All these were found to be successful with few or no problems encountered.

A number of bespoke C/HIP benchmarks were also constructed to look at host-device bandwidth and device-device bandwidth within a node. The results were broadly within expectations based on the AMD specifications. The Cray MPICH implementation also provides a GPU-aware MPI, where device memory references can be used directly in MPI API calls. This allows data transfer directly between GPUs both on-node, and via the network. Again, simple benchmarks suggested the bandwidths obtainable were in line with expectations. A C-code example that performed a sum reduction using all GPUs on one node using ROCm Collective Communications Library (RCCL) was also run successfully.

3.1 Debugging and Profiling

ROCm includes debugging and profiling tools, which are introduced in the courses available from the the ROCm Learning Center [10].

3.1.1 Debugging: ROCgdb and ROCTracer

The AMD ROCm Debugger (ROCgdb) is the AMD source-level debugger for Linux, which is based on the GNU Debugger. There is comprehensive documentation for this application available online on the AMD site [11].

ROCgdb works in the same way as `gdb` (except that the compilation flag is `-ggdb` instead of `-g`). There is additional functionality for debugging GPU kernel code. For example, breakpoints can be added to kernel functions and device code can be stepped through line-by-line. Information about different threads is available and a user can step through following the same thread or switching to another thread. Information about the GPU architecture is available, as is information about HIP API calls.

A programmatic interface that allows the developer to trace the execution of their GPU kernels is provided by ROCTracer. Again, simple tutorial examples were run successfully.

3.1.2 Profiling: rocProf and CrayPAT

The rocProf tool can be used for GPU profiling using hardware counters and application tracing. A simple GPU kernel was profiled twice, once to obtain basic statistics and again to record the total number of read and write requests by monitoring the relevant hardware counters.

Users of ARCHER2 will be familiar with CrayPAT, which is also available. A tutorial example was compiled with the `perftools-lite-gpu` module, and it was confirmed that the resulting profiling coverage included the GPU kernel. There was also information about data transfer to and from the GPU devices. Energy diagnostics are given at the node level but do not include network contributions.

3.2 Applications

This section gives the observations on building and running a number of scientific applications. In some cases indicative timings have been obtained for standard benchmarks both on ARCHER2 and the AMD GPU system and are reported on a node-for-node basis. The comparison of such results must be treated with considerable caution. So the results are included as of interest to readers, but do not pretend to be a rigorous performance comparison.

3.2.1 CP2K

CP2K [12] is a flexible open-source framework for quantum chemistry applications used in many domain areas. It is written in Fortran, and a number of elements of functionality may be offloaded to C++ and HIP.

CP2K 2022.1 was successfully built and tested by running a single-point energy calculation benchmark using 8 GPUs per node. The benchmark used H20 linear scaling density functional theory and featured 20,736 atoms in a 59 cubic angstrom box.

The results in Table 1 show the times for this benchmark on ARCHER2 (16 MPI tasks per node and 8 OpenMP threads per task) and pinoak (8 MPI tasks per node and 8 OpenMP host thread per task). The failure of strong scaling beyond two nodes on pinoak suggests that the benchmark is simply too small to occupy as many as 16 nodes (128 GPUs).

Nodes	ARCHER2 (s)	pinoak (s)	Ratio
1	705.0	324.3	2.2
2	384.8	164.5	2.3
4	206.6	108.8	1.9
8	115.7	61.8	1.9
16	65.6	50.1	1.3

Table 1: A comparison of the single-point energy benchmark run on ARCHER2 and pinoak. The time (seconds) for the benchmark is given, along with the relative performance.

3.2.2 GROMACS

GROMACS [13] is a molecular dynamics simulation code, which focuses on proteins, lipids and nucleic acids. It can be run on both CPUs and NVIDIA GPUs.

While the OpenCL element of GROMACS (version 2022.2) ran successfully with a trivial example, larger benchmarks were found to be problematic (with runtime failures). On this finding it was decided that, owing to the level of effort available, investigation of different GPU implementations in GROMACS would be avoided.

3.2.3 LAMMPS

LAMMPS is molecular dynamics simulation code which focuses on materials modeling [14]. It can be run on both CPUs and GPUs. A Kokkos-enabled version of LAMMPS was built using CPE 22.10 (PrgEnv-cray 8.3.3) and ROCm 5.0.2. Two variants of the standard Lennard-Jones LAMMPS benchmark were run, one featuring 8 million atoms, the other 27 million atoms. The ARCHER2 runs used 128 MPI tasks per node, whereas the pinoak runs had 8 MPI tasks per node (one for each GPU).

	8 million atoms			27 million atoms		
	time steps/day			time steps/day		
Nodes	ARCHER2	pinoak	Ratio	ARCHER2	pinoak	Ratio
1	10,657	58,096	5.45	1,874	16,824	8.98
2	28,643	92,828	3.24	5,092	28,249	5.55
4	61,574	153,908	2.50	13,778	53,387	3.87
8	129,632	239,715	1.85	34,086	97,169	2.85
16	240,929	347,443	1.44	71,747	169,575	2.36

Table 2: Standard LAMMPS Lennard-Jones benchmark using 8 million and 27 million atoms. The performance is measured as the number of simulation time steps per day of wall-clock time; higher figures are better performance. The relative performance is measured as a ratio.

3.2.4 Ludwig

Ludwig [15] is a code for complex fluids developed at The University of Edinburgh which includes a GPU implementation. This is achieved via a lightweight abstraction layer which has implementations for OpenMP, CUDA, and HIP. Execution proceeds via the usual model of offloading significant computational kernels to the GPU or GPUs. At the time of writing there is no GPU-aware MPI implementation, and explicit host-device transfers are required for halo exchanges. Ludwig is written in C.

The code compiles (either with `hipcc` or `cc`) and runs successfully on one or more GPUs. A number of observations are relevant.

1. Significant use of relocatable device code (device calls between different translation units) means that extremely long link times can occur, apparently because device code generation is deferred until link time. (This does not occur with `nvcc`.) There may be a case for refactoring the relevant functions to be `static inline` to avoid this problem, which may also improve general efficiency.
2. A problem was observed where apparent incorrect code optimisation at `-O3` caused a particular kernel to SEGV with a memory error (the same code gives the expected answer in both OpenMP and CUDA contexts). A work-around was identified at the expense of some performance. This remains under investigation.

Single GPU performance was similar to that observed for the Cirrus NVIDIA V100 for a standard benchmark. Further meaningful comparison for multiple GPU runs is deferred until a complete GPU-aware MPI implementation is available.

3.2.5 NAMD

NAMD [16] is a molecular dynamics program designed for high-performance simulations of very large biological objects on CPU and GPU architectures. NAMD is written in C++ and uses HIP to introduce GPU parallelism.

With some effort, a nightly version of NAMD (21 July 2022) was built and run successfully on `pinoak` using CPE 22.10 (PrgEnv-amd 8.3.3) and ROCm 5.0.2.

Two sizes (1M and 8M atoms) of the standard STMV benchmark were used. The larger STMV size required the memory optimised build of NAMD (used on both platforms). The ARCHER2 runs used 16 tasks per node, with each task having 7 worker threads and one communication thread. A similar arrangement was used for `pinoak`: 8 MPI tasks per node (one for each GPU), but no host threads.

	1 million atoms			8 million atoms		
	ns/day			ns/day		
Nodes	ARCHER2	<code>pinoak</code>	Ratio	ARCHER2	<code>pinoak</code>	Ratio
1	0.94	4.55	4.83	0.147	0.655	4.46
2	1.87	6.86	3.65	0.263	0.936	3.56
4	3.40	11.02	3.24	0.453	1.578	3.48
8	4.14	21.31	5.14	0.867	3.476	4.01
16	5.02	28.17	5.61	1.669	6.048	3.62

Table 3: NAMD STMV benchmark with 1 million atoms and 8 million atoms. The rate of progress is given in simulation nanoseconds per wall-clock day: higher figures are better performance.

In Table 3 the GPU speed-up shows no obvious decline with node count; in fact, for the 1M atom case, the largest speed-up is achieved with the highest node count (16). The GPU speed-up is between 3 and 4 for the 8M atom case.

3.2.6 PyFR

PyFR [17] is an open-source computational fluid dynamics framework for advection-diffusion problems on streaming architectures. The code is written in python and supports HIP and CUDA. PyFR 1.14.0 was installed and a standard airfoil test case was run on 2, 4 and 16 GPUs.

Table 4 shows that the AMD GPU is faster compared to the NVIDIA hardware on Cirrus by factors of 2.3 (2 GPUs) and 1.5 (16 GPUs). These results are classed as unsurprising on the basis of the relative hardware specifications.

NGPUs	NVIDIA V100 (CUDA 11.6)	AMD MI250X (ROCm 5.1.1)
2	180	80
4	88	51
16	22	15

Table 4: PyFR results on Cirrus and marvin4. Times are expressed in terms of minutes per timestamp file: lower figures are better performance.

3.2.7 Application summary

In this section we try to summarise the findings with a somewhat subjective judgement on the level of difficulty of the work involved in building and running each application. This is summarised in Table 5. A rating of easy, medium or difficult has been allocated to each code: this might be interpreted as whether a user, a developer, or a developer/expert support combination would be needed, respectively. It is stressed again that this report will not pass critical judgement on the recorded performance. The results should merely be regraded as an indication of what might be expected at a first attempt.

Application	Discipline	Model	Comments
CP2K	Quantum chemistry	Fortran/C++/HIP	Medium
GROMACS	MD (proteins)	C++/OpenCL	Not usable
LAMMPS	MD (materials)	C++/Kokkos/HIP	Medium/difficult
Ludwig	CFD (mesoscale)	C/HIP	Medium
NAMD	MD (biological mol.)	C++/HIP	Difficult
PyFR	CFD (aerofoil)	python/HIP	Easy

Table 5: A summary of applications and a subjective level of difficulty involved in building each one on the new system.

4 Conclusions

The ARCHER2 support team has had an opportunity to investigate a new technology based on AMD MI250X GPU hardware. The report has discussed attempts to build and run a number of HPC applications on the new platform. This assay included a range of applications from a number of disciplines, and also attempted to cover different GPU programming models.

In the introduction, a number of questions were set out.

1. Could the applications be built and run? Broadly, the situation was found to be positive. All the applications identified as potential candidates for the GPU system could be built and run, with the exception of GROMACS [18].
2. What was the level of tool support? While it is probably fair comment that the development of the AMD tool chain is not as mature as that available for NVIDIA platforms, all the existing tools were found to function as expected.
3. Could preliminary performance figures be reconciled with expectations? Initial performance measures were obtained for a limited set of benchmarks where figures were available for other GPU platforms, and were broadly consistent. Comparison with CPU results from ARCHER2 were included for interest only.
4. It was found that the existing training material developed for other UK services could be adapted with ease to the AMD platform.

On the broader question of whether a UK service could be based on this, or a related future technology, the work gives confidence that the support staff could gain relevant experience quickly and that applications could be built and run with reasonable effort.

Appendix A: Software versions

The main aspects of the hardware and software specifications for `marvin4` were:

- 16 GPU nodes each equipped with four AMD MI250X accelerators and one AMD EPYC 7A53 64-core processors (four 16-core NUMA regions), 512 GiB DRAM
- 32 CPU nodes each equipped with two AMD EPYC 7742 64-Core processors (eight 16-core NUMA regions), 256 GiB DRAM
- Slingshot 11 interconnect with one HPE Cray Cassini NIC per compute node (CPU and GPU)
- The Linux version was 5.3.18-150300.59.43.11.0.51-cray_shasta_c SUSE Linux Enterprise Server 15 SP3 and Cluster Manager Service Node 1.7.
- HPE Cray Performance Cluster Manager (HPCM) 1.7
- HPE Cray PE 22.04, 22.06
- ROCm 4.5.2, 5.0.2, 5.1.1
- Slurm 21.08.5 (login), 21.08.8-2 (compute)

There was no support for containers (e.g., Singularity) on `marvin4`.

Notes and References

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- [18] The authors are aware that GROMACS (and VASP) have been build at other sites with the same hardware since this work was carried out.